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Constraint faced by dairy farmers in different state of India: An overview

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Abstract

This review focus on the various constrain faced by dairy farmers in different states of India. Majority of the authors in northern states observed that lack of green fodder, high feed cost, poor AI were major constrains. Eastern states which are mostly have adverse climatic condition authors of these region observe constrain like lack of green fodder, problems of infertility in cattle, non-availability of artificial insemination (AI) centres, high cost of medicine. North-eastern region are mostly hilly region, dairy farmers over their observed low price of milk, lack in availability of green fodder, repeat breeding and improper treatment services were major constrain. Central states which include largest state of India dairy farmers there faced problems like low price of milk, farmers do not have superior animals, low producing local cows, poor quality feed and fodders. Similarly in west states poor irrigation facilities, time veterinary services and inadequate knowledge of diseases were major constrains. High cost of dairy animals, fodder and concentrate, poor conception rate of AI and high cost of labour and veterinary service were majorly faced constrain in Southern states.

Keywords: constrain, dairy farmers, conception rate, artificial insemination

Introduction

In India, most of livestock farmers belong to small house hold farming community and carrying out traditional practices. This study was carried out to know the main constraints faced by the livestock farmers in adopting dairy farming technology at grass root level. Evolution of dairying in India has a fascinating contextual. Nearly about five decades ago when the white revolution began and the dairy sector in India took leap forward to put the country on top of the world in terms of milk production. Previous to that, until the year 1955 or so, the milk production was very less and the per capita milk availability was insignificant. With the beginning of the first five year plan in 1951, India started to give a new look to the cattle breeding policy. In late sixties and early seventies, several projects like key village scheme (KVS) and intensive cattle development project (ICDP) were initiated giving way to the acceptance of cross-breeding in cattle. Milk in India is mostly produced by small-scale dairy farmers located in rural areas. Milk is perhaps, the only liquid that flows upwards; its production is carried out in widely dispersed production units in rural areas but its market is largely, in urban areas^[1]. For diary industry to be an assured source of income for the rural livestock owners and to provide the milk demand of city customers, these two groups of stakeholders have to be brought together. The challenge of connecting rural dairy farmers with city markets is compounded by the highly perishable nature of milk. Thus, processing is an important major component in milk chain, linking the producers to the consumers. However, raw milk produced in India is marketed in the mostly in unprocessed form, nevertheless the considerable dairy processing infrastructure that has been created in the country in the cooperative sector under the Operation Flood (OF) program.

The launch of Operation Flood -I, in the year 1970 revolutionized the dairy sector by establishing dairy farmer's co-operatives in the rural parts and linking them with the urban customers through an enormous system of milk obtaining, processing and delivering of milk to lakhs of villages in rural India. The loveliness of this program was that it completed the small dairy milk producers of India's dairying business through milk produce's cooperative societies. Operation Flood I started in 1970 to 1981 (13,000 village dairy cooperatives covering 15,000 farmers) was followed by Operation Flood II in 1981 to 1985 (34,500 village dairy cooperatives covering 36 lakh farmers) and Operation Flood III in 1985 to 1994

(73,300 village dairy cooperatives covering 9.4 million farmers). Several bull mother farms were established for production of exotic and crossbred bulls [2].

Livestock is most important constituent of economic and social life of the rural masses in India. Among all the possible livestock enterprises dairy farming is most popular and successful venture. The composition of milch animal stock has shifted towards greater domination of the buffaloes and crossbred cows and gradual to indigenous cows [3]. Dairying is in many ways the number one income for millions of rural households engaged in agriculture [4]. Animal husbandry is a significant sub-sector of the agriculture. Livestock sector plays a significant role in the Indian economy. India is devote with the largest livestock population in the world. More than 70% of people in India are engaged in vocations connected with farming and animal husbandry. India ranks first in milk production with 187.7 million tonnes of milk in 2018-19, out of those indigenous cattle contribute 11.3% and 9.5% by non-descriptive cattle [5]. To get the maximum return from livestock farming, optimum fertility of animals is necessary to be looked upon as production is indirectly related with reproductive traits [6]. Production potential of livestock depends on the different management practices. These practices vary across the agro-climatic regions due to numerous factors. To understand the livestock management practices followed by livestock owner in a region is necessary to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the rearing systems and to formulate suitable policy intervention. All the farmers did not keep their animals at a single place throughout the year or even for a whole day and night. Provision of good housing facilities to the animals not only reduces the energy wastage in maintaining thermos-neutral zone but also provides clean condition, reduces the incidence of diseases, protects them from predators and provides better working condition to the livestock owners. Health care management practices such as vaccination and deworming ensure proper health of animals that promotes their productivity. Management of reproduction is an important economic component in the success of a dairy enterprise. Inadequate heat detection has been identified as a major limit to herd reproductive performance over many years [7].

Livestock In India

More than 20.5 million people depend upon animal husbandry for their livelihood. Livestock contributed 16% to the income of small farm households as against an average of 14% for all rural households. Livestock is an important source of supplementary income for over 70 million rural households in India [8]. Livestock provides livelihood to 2/3 of rural community. It also provides employment to about 8.8% of the population in India. India has vast livestock resources.

Livestock sector contributes 4.11% GDP and 25.6% of total Agriculture GDP [9]. As per 20th total Livestock Census animal population is 535.78 million in the India which shows an increase of 4.6% over 19th Livestock Census. Total bovine population was 302.79 million in 2019 which shows an increase by 1.0%. The total number of cattle in the country is 192.49 million out of that exotic/crossbred and indigenous/non-descript cattle population in the country is 50.42 million and 142.11 million respectively. The total buffaloes in the country was 109.85 Million showing an increase of about 1.0% over previous census. Total milk population in country is 187.75 million tonnes which is increased by 6.5% over the previous year. The per capital milk availability is 394 gm/day. India's milk production continuously increased right from 1950-51, when the total milk production was 17 million tonnes [10].

Animal husbandry in India make a significant amount of world's livestock resources. Both the national economy as well as socio-economic growth of country is backed by the livestock sector. Besides offering great potential and outstanding contribution in agricultural sector over the past years, animal husbandry is performing well in the manner of production, value addition and export. Improving the productivity of livestock is one of the key tests. The average annual milk yield of Indian cattle is 1172 kg which is only about 50 per cent of the global average. The frequent outbreaks of diseases like FMD, BQ; Influenza, etc. continue to affect animal health and lowers animal productivity [11]. Largest population of ruminants contributes to greenhouse gases emission large amount. Crossbreeding of indigenous species with exotic stocks to enhance the genetic potential of different species has been successful only to a limited extent. Limited AI services owing to a deficiency in quality germ-plasm, infrastructure and technical manpower coupled with poor conception rate following artificial insemination have been the major impediments. In spite of remarkable achievement is done in milk production and other aspects of dairy development, country's share in the global trade is less than 1 per cent which is major thing that we can focus on. In order to become globally competitive and tapping the global dairy market to India's advantage, there is a need to switch to scientific management of all dairy operations including breeding, feeding, rearing and health care of animals and clean milk production. The focus has also to be on developing a range of value-added products and improve on processing methods [12]. In order to bring out this transformation first we have to examine where we standard what are the constraints limiting dairy production operations in India. Here present review attempts to highlight various constraints faced by the dairy farmers in different regions of the country based on published reports.

Table 1: Constraints faced by dairy farmers in different regions of the country

State	Jammu [13]
General	Lack of finance for A.H. management practices, high cost of raw material for dairy animal shed and inadequate housing, lack of proper knowledge of milk production economics
Feeding	High cost of feed supplements or mineral mixture, high cost of dry fodder and non-availability of pastureland
Breeding	Repeat breeding problem in dairy animals, poor conception rate of AI, lack of availability of breeding stock
Health	High cost of treatment and distant location of veterinary hospital
State	Himachal Pradesh [14]
General	Lack of training and scientific understanding to the farmers
Feeding	The dairy cattle are mostly fed with shuck and sheaves of dry grass. Continued supply of green fodder is apparently a distant dream for cattle in the state, so major constrain faced by farmer is lack of green fodder
Breeding	Lack of high yielding milch breed cattle

Health	Less active veterinary services and diagnostic services
State	Panjab ^[3]
General	Disposal of male calves, low price of crossbred cow milk, less fat content in cow milk
Feeding	Inadequate knowledge about balanced feeding, low availability of quality green fodder and dry fodder, high cost of feed and fodder
Breeding	Disposal of old/disabled cows unfit for breeding
Health	High morality in male calves and incidence of reproductive disorders
State	Uttarakhand ^[15]
General	Lack of transport, lack of standard pricing dairy farmers face a financial loss, lack of technological adoption, migration problem and water crises, lower milk production
Feeding	Dairy animals fed the crop residual and related outside house in the villages, imbalance diet and lack of proper nutrients and unavailability of green fodder which is huge demand for commercial dairy farming
Breeding	Unavailability of indigenous bulls of high genetic merit, poor conception rate through AI and irregular availability of semen at AI centre
Health	Lack of sufficient veterinary services and non-availability of vaccines
State	Haryana ^[16]
General	Non remunerative price of milk
Feeding	High price of concentrate mixture, low economic gains
Breeding	Inadequate facilities of AI and high prices of the imported semen straw
Health	Among the constraints in adoption of health care practices, the majority of farmers admitted that non availability of adequate veterinary services was the major problem
State	Uttar Pradesh ^[17]
General	Lack of knowledge of record keeping and waste disposal practices
Feeding	Lack of knowledge about recommended feeding practices of dairy animal
Health	Non-availability of timely treatment facilities and lack of knowledge of common contagious diseases, their prevention and control measures
State	Bihar ^[18]
General	Lack of scientific management, farmers not take services from vet. Experts nor consult only kept the traditional way and unavailability of improved breeds of livestock
Feeding	Lack of green fodder and lack of knowledge about balance feeding
Breeding	Problems of infertility in cattle as major constraint, lack of balanced feeding to the milch animals resulting in low growth and low reproductive performance
Health	Non-availability of skilled veterinary personnel in the villages and high cost of medicine and distance of govt. Veterinary hospital enhancing the health problem
State	Rajasthan ^[19]
General	No provision of subsidy on local animals, non-availability of staff during night and inappropriate working timings of hospital facilities and high expenses of medicines and treatment were perceived as 'most serious constraints
Feeding	Non-availability of feed and input material and fodder seeds
Breeding	Non availability or disgraceful of AI/PD at doorstep
Health	High cost of private veterinary services, less availability of qualified specialists, non-availability of emergency treatment at doorstep and lack of awareness about developmental programmes
State	Madhya Pradesh ^[20]
General	Lack of technical knowledge to manage the dairy, lack of storage facility of milk High cost of construction and lack of veterinary facility in village
Feeding	Do not give extra dose of concentrate to pregnant animal, farmer do not use mineral mixture/common salt in their feed and farmer do not feed chaffed fodder
Breeding	Farmers do not have cross breed/superior animals, farmers not follow AI, farmer not confirm the pregnancy by registered practitioner and farmer do not follow veterinary hospital for animal breeding
Health	Farmers do not follow regular cleaning/grooming of our animals, isolation of sick animals and hygienic steps before cleaning and farmers do not follow the vaccination against contagious diseases, farmers not properly follow the deworming.
State	Chhattisgarh ^[21]
General	Rearing of local cows, a dominant bovine species in tribal area was not profitable due to low productivity
Feeding	The poor quality feed and fodders, controlled grazing rotational grazing needed and rising feed and fodder costs
Breeding	Needed to improve performance of artificial insemination for up-gradation and network of cooperative societies
Health	The livestock support services were very poor in the state.
State	Jharkhand ^[22]
General	Lack knowledge about the livestock production and management practices, so there is a need to organize awareness camps
Feeding	Decreasing common grazing land
Breeding	Inadequate and distantly located artificial insemination facilities
Health	Lack of resources to purchase veterinary medicine
State	West Bengal ^[23]
General	Religion and caste create problems for selling milk, non-availability of pasture land is the major problem, because, according to the cropping sequence and there is very little time in a year, when the fields are vacant for grazing the animals
Feeding	Availability of green fodder is limited and with the limited land under fodder cultivation, there is need to focus to improve productivity of fodder crops and common grazing lands
Breeding	Repeat breeding problem is the major problem, non-availability of artificial insemination (AI) centres, lack of conviction towards AI, time of service to animals not known and non-availability of healthy bull respectively.
Health	High cost of veterinary services and lack of knowledge about vaccination schedule are constraints towards sustainable dairy farming

State	Odisha ^[12]
General	Scarcity of clean and safe water, inappropriate housing, management of animals in the wake of natural calamities like flood, cyclone and drought is difficult and daunting task
Feeding	Unavailability of green fodder, scarcity of dry fodder, mineral deficiency
Breeding	Failure of AI, abortion, lack of progeny tested male and infertility
Health	Most animals are infested with Entro and Ecto parasites.
State	Maharashtra ^[24]
General	Low milk production from the local breeds
Feeding	Shortage of green fodder and lack of clean water
Breeding	Non-availability of AI facility and timely services
Health	Inadequate knowledge of diseases, their prevention and control and non-availability of veterinary services.
State	Gujarat ^[25]
General	Lack of knowledge of recommended management practices, unavailability of loan for long duration and difficulty to store milk in summer season
Feeding	Poor irrigation facilities for cultivation of fodder crops
Breeding	Unavailability of timely AI facility at village
Health	Unavailability of on time veterinary services for treatment at door step
State	Telangana ^[26]
General	High cost of dairy animals and non-remunerative price for milk
Feeding	High cost of fodder & concentrate, scarcity of green fodder and dry fodder and lack of grazing facilities
Breeding	Non availability of breeding bulls locally, high incidence of repeat breeding and distant location of AI centres
Health	Non availability of veterinary services and high incidence of prolapse of uterus
State	Karnataka ^[27]
General	Low price of milk offered and low provision of loan in society or government. For purchasing cattle
Feeding	Lack of feed and fodder and high cost of production, unavailability of green fodder throughout the year and high cost of feed and fodder
Breeding	Poor conception rate through artificial insemination and lack of improved equipment occasional availability of semen at the AI centre
Health	Unavailability of vaccines, infrequent visit of veterinary staff, high cost of veterinary medicines and high charges of emergency veterinary services
State	Tamil Nadu ^[28]
General	Lack of availability of labour and lack of insurance facility
Feeding	Unavailability of green fodder round the year and high cost of cattle feed and mineral mixture and lack of community grazing land
Breeding	The distance to AI centre/hospital, infertility problem and poor conception rate of ai and problem of abortion and unable to detect heat symptoms
Health	The vulnerability of cross-bred animals to diseases and lack of knowledge about disease prevention and high cost of medicine
State	Kerala ^[29]
General	High labour cost and high interest rate on cattle loan
Feeding	High cost of cattle feed and non-availability of green and dry fodder round the year
Breeding	Non-availability of high yielding milch animals
Health	High cost of veterinary service and medicine
State	Assam ^[30]
General	Lack of rearing area for livestock, conflict with wild animals and lack of knowledge on rearing system of livestock
Feeding	Scarcity of fodder
Health	Lack in timely treatment and vaccination of livestock
State	Mizoram ^[31]
General	Lack of organized marketing facility and low price of milk and high milk price fluctuation were the major marketing problems in dairying
Feeding	Inadequate dry and green fodder, high cost of concentrate feed and inadequate knowledge about balanced feeding and inadequate concentrate
Breeding	Lower conception rate through AI, unavailability of AI facility on time, problems of heat detection and poor quality of sire at village and repeat
Health	Lack of veterinary facility, lack of credit facility and incidence of reproductive disorder in milch animals
State	Nagaland ^[32]
General	Low price of milk and delay in payment by unorganized sector and lack of knowledge about improved dairy practices
Feeding	Lack of availability of green fodder, inadequate knowledge about balanced feeding Low availability and high cost of concentrates
Breeding	Repeat breeding in cows and high incidence of reproductive disorders
Health	Improper treatment services and problem of heat detection in cows

Table -1 gives us strong view on different constrain faced by dairy farmers through the country which directly affecting livestock owners. A brief summarized interpretation of the different states constrain discussed below.

Constrain observed on northern states

Constrain faced by respondents from Doda district of Jammu

like lack of finance, lack knowledge, high feed cost, poor AI, repeat breeding and high cost of treatments were serious constrain in their region. In hilly track of Himachal Pradesh respondents faced constrains lacking of farmers training, lack of green fodder, Lack of high yielding milch breed. Similarly in Uttarakhand lack of transport, lack of standard pricing, unavailability of green fodder and indigenous breeding bull

and lack of sufficient veterinary services were major constrain. Punjab and Haryana were in top ten milk producing state in India, respondents from both state face non remunerative price of milk, high cost of feed and fodder and incidence of reproductive disorders were major constrains. Lack of knowledge of record keeping, recommended feeding practices and common contagious diseases prevention and control measures were perceived constrain in Uttar Pradesh. Similarly in second highest milk producing state Rajasthan dairy farmers faced subsidy on local animal purchasing, non-availability of feed and fodder, Non availability or disgraceful of A.I. / P.D. at doorstep and high cost of private veterinary services were major faced problems.

Constrain observed on eastern states

Bihar, Jharkhand, West Bengal and Odisha were among the eastern region states of India. Lack of scientific management of livestock, lack of green fodder, problems of infertility in cattle, Non-availability of artificial insemination (AI) centres, high cost of medicine and decreasing common grazing land were major constrain faced by eastern states. Odisha is known as disaster capital of India famers over there mostly facing scarcity of clean and safe water, unavailability of green fodder and dry fodder and problem of ecto and endo parasitic infestation was major problem [12].

Constrain observed on north-eastern states

Assam is highest milk producing state among north-eastern states with 882 million litres [33]. Constrain faced by dairy owners their include high cost labour and feed, lack of financial assistance to dairy and high calf mortality in calf were major problems. Nagaland rank 5th in milk production among seven sister state with 73 million litres milk production. Low price of milk, lack in availability of green fodder, repeat breeding and improper treatment services were major constrain. While Mizoram which is lowest milk producing state among north-eastern state faced constrain like lack of organized marketing facility, inadequate dry and green fodder, unavailability of AI facility on time and lack of veterinary facility [33].

Constrain observed on central states

Madhya Pradesh is one of three top milk producing state of India, low price of milk and milk products, farmers do not aware about scientific feeding practices, farmers do not have superior animals for breeding and not follow the vaccination in animals were major constrain in state. Chhattisgarh farmers faced problems like rearing of low producing local cows, poor quality feed and fodders and not getting livestock support services.

Constrain observed on west states

Gujarat and Maharashtra are two state which possess most number of recognised Indigenous dairy breeds of cattle and buffalo. Farmers over their faced problem like lack of knowledge of recommended management practices, poor irrigation facilities for cultivation of fodder crops, unavailability of on time veterinary services, low milk production from the local buffalo breeds and inadequate knowledge of diseases, their prevention and control.

Constrain observed on south states

The Telangana state is ranked eighth in livestock population and 13th in milk production. Farmer majorly facing problems

like high cost of dairy animals, high cost of fodder & concentrate, non-availability of breeding bulls locally and Non availability of veterinary services. Nearby state Tamil Nadu ranks among the top ten milk producing states of the country with a daily production of 206 lakh litres per day. Farmers over there facing constrains like lack of availability of labour, unavailability of green fodder round the year, infertility problem and poor conception rate of AI and the vulnerability of cross-bred animals to diseases. Karnataka ranks 11th in overall milk production in the country though the State is the second largest milk producer in the cooperative sector after Gujarat. Major problems faced by dairy farmers include low price of milk, lack of feed and fodder, high cost of production, poor conception rate through AI and high cost of veterinary medicines. National Dairy Research Institute (NDRI), Karnal, on dairy production systems in the country has given Kerala the top spot overall among 20 milk-producing States [34]. Kerala stood first in three categories animal breeding, resource availability and policies and regulations. Even though problem of high labour cost, high cost of cattle feed, non-availability of high yielding milch animals and high cost of veterinary service and medicine were major contain faced by dairy farmers.

Conclusion

Global demand of milk is growing by 15 million tons per year, mostly in developing countries like India. In changing global scenario it is required to educate farmers regarding scientific management of dairy animals, operations like clean milk production, processing, preservation, storage and transport of milk and milk products are required to know importance. Based on above discussion it intimated that constrain like lack of proper knowledge regarding scientific management of dairy animals, inadequate knowledge about balanced feeding with lack in good quality feed and fodder availability, unavailability of high genetic merit indigenous bulls, poor conception rate through AI and lack of sufficient veterinary services were major constrain to cope up. In order for India to become a leading performer at world level need to make strategy to solve ground level problems of farmers.

References

1. Sirohi S, Kumar A, Staal SJ. Formal milk processing sector in Assam: Lessons to be learnt from institutional failure. *Agricultural Economics Research Review* 2009;22(347-2016-16857):245-254.
2. <https://www.nddb.coop/about/genesis/flood>
3. Dhindsa SS, Nanda R, Kumar B. Problems and constraints of dairy farming in Fatehgarh Sahib District of Punjab. *Progressive Research* 2014;9(1):250-252.
4. Nalwaya SB, Prajapati BI, Bariya AR, Goswami MM, Roy SK. Evaluation of Physico-Chemical and Microbiological Quality of Milk of Banaskantha District, India. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences* 2018;7(12):1635-1641.
5. Savalia KB, Ahlawat AR, Gamit VV, Parikh SS, Verma AD. Recently recognized indigenous cattle breeds of India: A review. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences* 2019;8(12):161-168.
6. Verma AD, Panigrahi M, Baba NA, Sulabh S, Sadam A, Parida S *et al.* Differential expression of ten candidate genes regulating prostaglandin action in reproductive tissues of buffalo during estrous cycle and pregnancy. *Theriogenology* 2018;105:7-14.

7. Gamit VV, Rao TKS, Parikh SS, Gamit PM. Advanced heat detection aids and its applications in dairy farm. *Scholars Journal of Agriculture and Veterinary Sciences* 2015;2:287-294.
8. Patel SJ, Kumar R, Patel AS, Patel NR, Parmar VN. Involvement of Farm Women in Decision making Regarding Dairy Farming in Junagadh District of Gujarat State. *Indian Journal of Hill Farming* 2017;30(1):45-58.
9. Vikaspedia. (n.d.). Vikaspedia. Retrieved December 10, 2020, from <http://vikaspedia.in>
10. Anonymous. 20th Livestock Census Report - 2019. All India Report. Department of Animal Husbandry, Dairying and Fisheries, Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, GoI, New Delhi 2019.
11. <http://agrospectrumindia.com/analysis/28/159/livestock-sector-in-india-trends-challenges-and-a-way-forward.html>
12. Singh RK. Livestock research and development priorities for Bihar and Odisha. Available at SSRN 2391607 2013.
13. Minhaj SU, Khandi SA, Bafanda RA, Bhushan B, Choudhary F, Khateeb AM. Constraints Perceived by Dairy Farmers in the Adoption of Improved Animal Husbandry Practices in Doda District. *International Journal of Livestock Research* 2019;9(2):319-326.
14. Dogra A, Dairy Development in Himachal Pradesh. *Journal of Advances and Scholarly Researches in Allied Education* 2016;12(23):366-368.
15. Pant S, Yadav AS, Joshi J. Dairy development in almora and environs: Role of almora dugdh Utpadak Sahakari Sangh Limited (Adussl), Almora, Uttarakhand. *Zenith International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2019;9(3):250-261.
16. Singh PR, Bhatti JS, Hundal JS, Kansal SK. Constraints faced by farmers in adoption of dairy as entrepreneurship. *Haryana Veterinarian* 2015;54(1):67-69.
17. Singh AK, Gupta J, Singh M, Patel D. Constraints faced by the dairy farmers in adopting good farming practices in Uttar Pradesh. *International Journal of Agricultural Science and Research* 2017;7(4):123-130.
18. Bhutia TL, Kamal RK, Mohanty S, Kumar U. Constraints analysis in the crop-livestock farming systems of small and marginal farmers of Bihar. *SKUAST Journal of Research* 2017;19(1):92-96.
19. Singodia M, Rewani SK, Baidha A, Chand S, Rajoria S, Singh V. Constraints Faced By Livestock Farmers in Utilization of Livestock Services in Jaipur District of Rajasthan, *Indian Research Journal of Extension Education* 2019;19(2, 3):104-107.
20. Rajpoot JS, Kirad KS, Badaya AK, Chauhan SS. Constraints faced by dairy farmers while adopting animal management practices in Dhar District of Madhya Pradesh, India. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences* 2018;7(01):3163-3166.
21. Chand P, Sirohi S, Saxena R, Mishra A. How profitable is dairying in tribal Chhattisgarh? *Indian Journal of Animal Sciences* 2018;88(6):749-754.
22. Kumar M, Gupta J, Radhakrisnan MSA. Constraints in Livestock Production Systems Faced by Tribes of Ranchi and Dhanbad districts of Jharkhand. *Research Journal of Agricultural Sciences* 2015;6(3):662-665.
23. Bera R, Seal A, Das TH, Sarkar D. Constrains Perceived by the Dairy Farmers in Irrigated Ecosystem: A Case Study from Damodar Command Area, West Bengal. *Research & Reviews: Journal of Dairy Science and Technology* 2018;7(1):1-5.
24. Patil AP, Gawande SH, Nande MP, Gobade MR. Constraints faced by the dairy farmers in Nagpur district while adopting animal management practices. *Veterinary World* 2009;2(3):111.
25. Pata BA, Odedra MD, Savsani HH, Ahlawat AR, Patbandha TK, Marandi S. Constraints Faced by Buffalo Owners in Junagadh and Porbandar Districts of Gujarat. *Journal of Animal Research* 2018;8(6):1081-1085.
26. Rajsekhar M, Ranjana N, Mahindar M, Satya N. A critical analysis of constraints faced by the urban and peri urban dairy farmers in and around Hyderabad city of Telangana. *Indian Journal of Animal Production and Management* 2017;33(1, 2):11-14.
27. Harisha M, Desai AR, Gopala GT, Biradar C, Savanur M. Dairy Production Constraints in Kolar and Chikkaballapur Districts of Karnataka. *International Journal of Livestock Research* 2019;9(10):148-154.
28. Kavithaa NV, Rajkumar NV, Manokaran S. Constraints in dairy farming: a critical analysis among the dairy farmers of Tamil Nadu. *International Journal of Science, Environment and Technology* 2020;9(3):407-412.
29. Smitha S, Devi MCA, Subash S. "Analysis of Constraints in Dairy Farming in Kerala-Multi Stakeholder Perspective." *Indian Journal of Dairy Science* 2019;72(3):342-46.
30. Borah B, Borgohain A, Ray MN, Khuman LS, Borthakur B, Debbarman C, Payeng S *et al.* Constraints Faced By the Farmers of Fringe Villages of Kaziranga National Park in Livestock Rearing, Assam, India. *International Journal of Educational Science and Research* 2017;7(2):27-30.
31. Malhotra R, Priscilla L. Economics of milk production and its constraints in Mizoram. *Indian Journal of Dairy Science* 2016;69(5):588-594.
32. Khovel LLM, Jain DK, Chauhan AK. Economics of milk production and its constraints in Nagaland. *Indian Journal of Dairy Science* 2012;65(6):520-526.
33. <https://www.nddb.coop/information/stats/milkprodstate>
34. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/kerala/kerala-tops-ndri-study-on-dairy-production/article31076118.ece>